

The Deposition of Thin Films in a Radio Frequency Glow Discharge*

S. P. Mukherjee

Thin films of organometallic polymers and metal oxides have been prepared by the decomposition of organo-metallic compounds in radio frequency (1 Mc/Sec) glow discharge; compounds used were tetra-ethoxy silane, *n*-butyl titanate, etc. The process consists in exposing the substrate to a glow discharge atmosphere of a background gas (either oxygen or argon) and the organometallic compound vapour in the pressure range of 0.1 mm to 1 mm Hg. The rate of deposition is a function of various deposition parameters. The substrates used were metals, silicon-semiconductor, vitreous silica, sodium chloride single crystals, plastic sheets. The infra-red spectroscopic studies of the films show that when oxygen is used as background gas *i.e.*, in oxygen plasma, metal oxide (non-crystalline) films are formed, but in argon plasma or in absence of any background gas organo-metallic polymer films are formed.

The investigations of the deposition of films using aluminium chloride as the metal source shows that the glow discharge reaction of either (a) AlCl_3 with $(\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2)$ or (b) AlCl_3 with O_2 produces non-crystalline aluminium oxides.

The application of gas discharge for the synthesis of simple gaseous compounds *e.g.* ozone, nitric oxide, etc. has been known for a long time. The formation of organic polymers in a glow discharge has also been known for many years. Only recently, however, has the glow discharge been applied to the deposition of organic polymer films¹. The deposition of the films of inorganic solids *e.g.* silicon, silica, silicon nitride by a glow discharge reaction is an even newer development^{2,3,4}. Alt, Ing and Laendle² reported the deposition of amorphous silica films by the decomposition of tetra-ethoxy silane in a high frequency glow discharge. Sterling and Swann³ deposited (a) amorphous silicon from silane, (b) silica from a mixture of silane and nitrous oxide, (c) silicon nitride from a mixture of silane and ammonia. In this process, the reactant gases are subjected to a gas discharge at pressure of about 0.1 mm Hg and deposition takes place on substrate placed near the region of the glow at a low ambient temperature.

The present work describes the deposition of the films of metal oxides and organo-metallic polymers by the decomposition of various organo-metallic compounds in radio frequency (1 MC/Sec) glow discharge. The work also describes the preliminary studies done on the deposition of thin films of alumina using aluminium halide as metal source.

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1. J. Goodman, *J. Polymer. Sc.*, 1960, **44**, 531.
2. L. I. Alt, S. W. Ing, and K. W. Leandle, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1963.
3. H. F. Sterling and R. C. G. Swann, *Solid State Electronics*, 1965, **8**, 653.
4. D. R. Secrist and J. D. Mackenzie, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1966, **113**, 914.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : The following organo-metallic compounds were used :

- i) Tetra-ethoxy silane : $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$, liquid at room temperature;
- ii) Tetra-*n*-butyl orthotitanate : $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_4$, liquid at room temperature;
- iii) Aluminium-tert-Butoxide : $\text{Al}[\text{O.C.}(\text{CH}_3)_3]_3$, white powder, sublimes in high vacuum;
- iv) Aluminium acetyl-acetonate : $\text{Al}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{O}_2)_3$, white powder distils without decomposition at 140° .

Substrates used were nickel discs, niobium discs, silicon semiconductor discs, transparent vitreous silica discs, and sodium chloride single crystals. Surfaces of all substrates were finely polished and thoroughly cleaned.

Apparatus and deposition procedure : The glow discharge chamber is a vertical transparent vitreous silica tube which can be maintained at low pressure, under a sustained gas flow. A schematic diagram of flow system is given in Fig. 1. The primary objective

Schematic Diagram of the flow system used for Glow Discharge deposition of thin films.

Fig. 1

of the glow discharge apparatus was to expose the substrate to a controlled atmosphere of metal compound vapour and a back-ground gas. When organometallic compounds were used as the metal source, the background gas used was either argon or oxygen. For the deposition of aluminium oxide from aluminium chloride either oxygen or a mixture of hydrogen and carbon dioxide was used. The concentration of the vapour or the vapour flow rate was controlled by controlling the temperature of the metal-compound source. The radio frequency (1 MC/Sec) power was applied to the gas through a copper coil fitting closely to the tube. There was arrangement for heating the substrates by means of a tubular electrical resistance heater introduced underneath the substrate stand.

The following sequence of operations was adopted for the deposition process :

- i) A clean substrate was placed on the substrate stand.
- ii) The discharge tube was evacuated to a pressure of 0.005 mm Hg.
- iii) The r.f. power was adjusted so that a glowing plasma impinging on the substrate surface was generated and the substrate was cleaned with the discharge.
- iv) After the discharge cleaning, the background gas (argon or oxygen or a mixture of H_2 and CO_2) was introduced from the top and the metal compound vapour was introduced through the side tube. The total pressure during deposition was different with different metal compounds. In the case of organo-metallic compounds, it was in the range 0.1 mm Hg to 1 mm Hg. In the case of aluminium chloride, it was in the range 0.5 mm to 2 mm Hg.
- v) The deposition process was run for a definite period under this continuous flow system. After the run, the deposition rate was measured.

The physical appearance, chemical nature and structure of the films deposited were investigated with the help of optical microscopy, electron-microscopy and infra-red spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Films from Organo-metallic Compounds : The chemical composition of the films is strongly influenced by the ratio of the concentration of oxygen and organo-metallic compounds in the reaction chamber. In argon atmosphere or in absence of any back-ground gas, organo-metallic polymer films are deposited but when oxygen concentration in the reaction chamber is sufficiently high, non-crystalline oxide films are deposited.

Both polymeric and oxide films were transparent, smooth, strongly adherent and free of pin holes. All films deposited, irrespective of experimental conditions, were non-crystalline and isotropic. Very broad diffuse bands seen in the electron diffraction patterns of thin films and X-ray diffraction powder patterns proved the absence of any long range order in the film structure.

Systematic investigation of the effect of nature and concentration of background gas on the chemical composition and structure of the films was done with films obtained from tetra-ethoxy silane. The spectra of one film deposited in argon plasma and two films deposited in oxygen plasma at different concentrations of oxygen were recorded for comparison. The spectrum of the film deposited in absence of any background gas was found to be identical to that of the films deposited in an argon plasma. The absorption bands of these three spectra and their provisional assignment to the characteristic frequencies are given in Table 1. The infrared spectra of the films deposited in argon or in the absence of any background gas compare well with the spectra of poly-ethoxy silane⁵ produced by the hydrolytic condensation of tetra-ethoxy silanes.

A comparison of the spectra of the films deposited with increasing ratio of oxygen to tetra-ethoxy silane vapour shows that with increase of oxygen concentration, (i) the intensities of the bands due to hydrocarbons diminishes and ultimately the bands disappear;

5. A. N. Lazarev, *Optics and Spectroscopy*, 1960, **8**, 325.

(ii) the sharpness of the shoulder at 1165 cm^{-1} diminishes and the shoulder disappears at sufficiently high oxygen concentration; (iii) the absorption band due to Si-O-Si stretching shifts from 1075 cm^{-1} to 1065 cm^{-1} ; (iv) the band at 960 cm^{-1} shifts to 925 cm^{-1} . The effects of increasing oxygen concentration on the films can be explained on considering the mechanism of the reaction suggested by Mukherjee⁶ from his work on the kinetics of the deposition process.

TABLE 1

Infrared absorption bands and their provisional assignment (wave numbers in cm^{-1})

Deposited in Argon	Desposited in Oxygen		Provisional assignment
	Temperature		
	Low	High	
3600-3100 (br) 3580 (w)	3600-3000 (br) 3580 (w)	3600-3000 (br) 3580 (w)	Liquid water as absorbed layers, OH involved in hydrogen bonding, structural OH, adsorbed NH_3 , adsorbed NH_4^+ .
2970 (m)	2970 (m)	—	CH, CH_3 stretching.
2930 (w)	2930 (vw)	—	CH_2 stretching.
2890 (w)	2890 (w)	—	CH (tertiary),
—	1690 (w)	1690 (w)	Free OH, deformation.
1445 (w)	1445 (w)	—	CH deformation, C- CH_3 ,
1380 (m)	1380 (m)	—	C- CH_3 , C-(CH_3) ₂ .
1255 (w)	—	—	$\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)$, $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2$.
1165 (sh)	1165 (sh)	1165 (vw, sh)	Si-O- C_2H_5 .
1100 (vw, sh)	—	—	Si-O-Si.
1075 (s)	1070 (s)	1065 (s)	Si-O- C_2H_5
960 (m)	950 (m)	925 (m)	Si-O-Si, Si-O- C_2H_5 , Si-OH.
880 (w)	880 (w)	—	Si-C stretching.
790 (m)	790 (m)	790 (w)	$\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)$. Si-O- C_2H_5 , Si-O-Si.

vw = very weak; w = weak; m = medium; s = strong; sh = shoulder; br = broad.

For comparison see :

- L. J. Bellamy, *Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules*, Methuen, London, 1959,
L. H. Little, *Infra-red Spectra of Adsorbed Species*, Academic Press, London, 1966,

According to the mechanism suggested⁶, in oxygen plasma, the interaction of organo-metallic compound molecules with energised oxygen species *i.e.* atomic oxygen takes place. It is, therefore, a combustion process where $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$ molecules interact with atomic oxygen to produce silicon oxygen species and the combustion of hydrocarbons gives $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ if sufficient oxygen is present. Hence it is expected that with increase of oxygen concentration the gradual disappearance of the bands due to hydrocarbons will occur. The cause of shifting of the band due to Si-O-Si from 1075 cm^{-1} (in polymer film) to 1065 cm^{-1}

6. S. P. Mukhopadhyay (Mukherjee), Ph.D. Thesis, University of Manchester (1967).

(in oxide film) may be due to the absence of the interaction of C-O bond on Si-O-Si bonds in oxide structure. The spectra of the films deposited at 40° (substrate temperature) in plasma having sufficiently high oxygen concentration is similar to that of amorphous hydrated silica films containing both structural and absorbed hydroxyl groups. The absorption band at 925 cm⁻¹ is due to structural hydroxyl group and gradually disappear with increase of substrate temperature.

The results obtained from the investigation with other organo-metallic compounds are similar in nature. However, no detail systematic studies were done in these cases. The results of infra-red spectroscopic studies of the films deposited by the decomposition of *n*-butyl titanate show that when the oxygen to organo-metallic compound vapour ratio is high the film formed is non-crystalline titanium oxide, but when the oxygen to vapour ratio is low, the film formed is an organo-metallic polymer. The polymeric film deposited in the present case may be like the polymer obtained by the hydrolysis of *n*-butyl titanate⁷. The film of titanium oxide free from hydrocarbon incorporation is of amorphous nature as indicated by the electron diffraction pattern.

The results of preliminary work on the deposition of films by the decomposition of organo-aluminium compounds show that the films deposited by the decomposition of Al-tert-butoxide were transparent, pinhole free and polymeric (as indicated by the colour and hardness). The films deposited by the decomposition of Al-acetyl acetonate was white, non-coherent and powdery. The I.R. absorption bands present in one such film are at 1140 cm⁻¹ and 1040 cm⁻¹. These bands correspond to the bands due to Al-OH (at 1162-900 cm⁻¹) in anodic oxide films⁸.

Deposition of Alumina using Aluminium Chloride as Metal Source : The deposition of aluminium oxide on the basis of the following two reactions was investigated :

Investigation of the gas discharge reaction of AlCl₃ either in a plasma of carbon-dioxide and hydrogen or in oxygen show that deposition of films takes place under proper experimental conditions. It was observed that with a low concentration of AlCl₃ vapour in the reaction chamber the films were coherent, but the deposit becomes non-coherent and powdery at higher concentration of AlCl₃.

The adhesion of the films to the glass substrates was not strong. The colour of the film was white, but occasionally brownish white deposits were obtained. The films were insoluble in conc. HCl and in dil. NaOH solution. The electron diffraction pattern and X-ray diffraction powder pattern of the films indicate the absence of long range order. However, from their physical appearance and resistance to chemical attack it can be said that white films are amorphous alumina films. The brownish white films may be partially oxidised aluminium chloride. The formation of a viscous liquid like substance, thought to be Si₃O₂Cl₂ or Si₂OCl₄ during the deposition of SiO₂ from the pyrolytic reaction of SiCl₄ with (CO₂+H₂) is reported⁸. The brownish white deposit obtained in this work during the deposition of

7. T. N. Trylova and G. O. Bagdyk'Yants, *Optics and Spectroscopy*, 1960, **9**, 339.

8. G. A. Dorsey, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1966, **113**, 169.

Al_2O_3 may be a similar intermediate complex. It can be observed from the transmission electron micrograph of a film that the film is not perfectly homogeneous in structure, the presence of structural heterogeneity in the form of minute particles of about 600Å in diameter can be discerned. The film appeared to be an agglomerate of minute particles. It can, therefore, be suggested that these minute particles form in the vapour phase by the vapour phase nucleation or clustering. This can be supported by the fact that charged species such as ions can easily serve as a condensation centre in vapour phase in the formation of clusters and colloidal particles.^{9,10}

It can be concluded that the adherent pinhole free films of organo-metallic polymer and metal oxides can be deposited by the radio frequency glow discharge technique. Unlike pyrolytic deposition process, the heating of the substrate is not necessary. The deposition can, therefore, be effected at a wide range of substrate temperatures. Many high temperature inorganic solids *e.g.*, oxides, nitrides, carbides, borides etc., can be deposited on a wide variety of substrates including plastics, glass, semi-conductors and metals.

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Department of Chemistry,
Presidency College,
Calcutta-12.

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9. W. Steinmaier and J. Bloom, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1964, **111**, 206.
10. E. J. Hellund, *The Plasma State*, Reinhold Publishing Co., New York, 1961, p. 30.
11. H. S. W. Massey and E. H. S. Burhop, *Electronic and Ionic Impact Phenomena*, Clarendon Press, Oxford 1952, p. 414.